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Key Points:

- The lag-1 autocorrelation pattern of daily precipitation in the tropics is robust across different observation-based data sets
- The lag-1 autocorrelation reflects the relative variance of high frequency and low frequency convectively coupled equatorial waves
- Kilometer-scale models capture the observed autocorrelation, but models with parameterized deep convection overestimate it

Supporting Information:

Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

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Autocorrelation—A Simple Diagnostic for Tropical Precipitation Variability in Global Kilometer-Scale Climate Models

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Abstract We propose the lag-1 autocorrelation of daily precipitation as a simple diagnostic of tropical precipitation variability in climate models. This metric generally has a relatively uniform distribution of positive values across the tropics. However, selected land regions are characterized by exceptionally low autocorrelation values. Low values correspond to the dominance of high frequency variance in precipitation, and specifically of high frequency convectively coupled equatorial waves. Consistent with previous work, we show that CMIP6 climate models overestimate the autocorrelation. Global kilometer-scale models capture the observed autocorrelation when deep convection is explicitly simulated. When a deep convection parameterization is used, though, the autocorrelation increases over land and ocean, suggesting that land surface-atmosphere interactions are not responsible for the changes in autocorrelation. Furthermore, the metric also tracks the accuracy of the representation of the relative importance of high frequency and low frequency convectively coupled equatorial waves in the models.

Plain Language Summary Rainfall in the tropics is influenced by many atmospheric processes that depend on geographic location. We use the lag-1 autocorrelation as a metric for the day-to-day persistence of rainfall. We find that rainfall is very persistent in most parts of the tropics with a few exceptions over land, for example, the Sahel, where high frequency rainfall events dominate. Our results show that models with a horizontal resolution of a few kilometers reproduce the autocorrelation, in contrast to coarser climate models. We also analyze atmospheric waves and find that they are important for the autocorrelation pattern in the observations and the simulations.

1. Introduction

Precipitation in the tropics is, for the most part, the result of deep convection and is modulated by an intricate interplay of various different processes. The convective systems associated with much tropical rainfall are not of purely random nature, but are often organized by larger scale dynamics, ranging from mesoscale convective systems (MCSs) to synoptic scale convectively coupled equatorial waves (CCEWs) and the planetary scale Madden-Julian Oscillation (MJO) (Cheng et al., 2023; Cho et al., 2004; Feng et al., 2021; Kiladis et al., 2009; Wheeler & Kiladis, 1999). Thus, the day-to-day variability or rather persistence of tropical precipitation varies by location. Some of these geographic distinctions are captured by the lag-1 autocorrelation of daily precipitation, as presented by Roehrig et al. (2013), who used observation-based precipitation data from GPCP, and as shown below. Simply put, lag-1 autocorrelation is a measure of persistence. For example, high persistence of precipitation over several days will result in a high lag-1 autocorrelation. High variance of precipitation over the same period, on the other hand, will result in a low lag-1 autocorrelation.

Roehrig et al. (2013) further showed that the global climate models (GCMs) that are part of CMIP5 (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5) all overestimate the lag-1 autocorrelation in the western Sahel region compared to GPCP. Moon, Gudmundsson, et al. (2019) interpreted the overestimation of precipitation persistence over global land in CMIP5 models compared to observations in terms of soil moisture feedbacks, but a different interpretation is possible. Low resolution GCMs may be misrepresenting deep convection, its organization, or its coupling to the larger scale (e.g., CCEWs). This suggestion is consistent with previous work showing that CMIP models generally misinterpret tropical precipitation (Fiedler et al., 2020; Palmer & Stevens, 2019).

Unlike low resolution GCMs, kilometer-scale models are run with horizontal grid spacings of a few kilometers and with deep convection simulated explicitly. As a result, many precipitation characteristics—such as its diurnal cycle, location and spatial propagation—have been shown to be more accurately represented in kilometer-scale models (Stevens et al., 2020). Kilometer-scale models can also simulate many aspects of MCSs and related processes, which is not possible for most low resolution GCMs (see Feng et al. (2023) and sources within). The ability to correctly simulate MCSs is crucial, since MCSs produce more than 50% of tropical precipitation (Feng et al., 2021). The benefits of high resolutions also accrue to aspects of the large scale dynamics. For example, Judt and Rios-Berrios (2021) illustrated that the Model for Prediction Across Scales-Atmosphere (MPAS) produces more realistic precipitation variances associated with what we will call HF-CCEWs (high frequency CCEWs, with a lower frequency limit of 0.2 day^{-1}) when the resolution is refined to a few kilometers and deep convection is explicitly simulated. Moreover, Tomassini (2018) demonstrated that convection and African easterly waves (a type of HF-CCEWs) are dynamically linked through mesoscale circulations. This poses a challenge to deep convection parameterizations. Kilometer-scale models, on the other hand, explicitly represent this mesoscale coupling mechanism and therefore could remedy shortcomings of traditional GCMs with respect to the timing of rainfall events in the tropics.

This study aims to introduce the lag-1 autocorrelation of daily precipitation as a simple diagnostic to assess tropical precipitation variability in kilometer-scale climate models. To this end, we first address the question of whether the lag-1 autocorrelation pattern is robust across different satellite-based observations and gauge station time series. We then investigate whether global kilometer-scale models are capable of producing lag-1 autocorrelation values comparable to the observations. Finally, we analyze CCEWs as a possible cause of the lag-1 autocorrelation pattern.

The paper is structured as follows. Data and methods are detailed in Section 2. We present the lag-1 autocorrelation of daily precipitation in Section 3.1 for multiple observations, global kilometer-scale simulations, and CMIP6 models. In Section 3.2 we examine the contribution of CCEWs to tropical precipitation variance and its connection to the lag-1 autocorrelation. Conclusions and further discussion are given in Section 4.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Data

We use daily accumulated precipitation from three global kilometer-scale climate models which we denote as ICON, IFS, and MPAS. ICON-Sapphire (Hohenegger et al., 2023) and IFS coupled to the FESOM ocean model (Rackow et al., 2024) are part of the nextGEMS project. We analyze their cycle 3 simulations (covering 2020–2024) but also include cycle 2 simulations (covering 2020) of the IFS model and coarser simulations with IFS coupled to the NEMO ocean model. While the ICON simulation was only run without deep convection parameterization, IFS was run both with and without deep convection parameterization at both resolutions. In the IFS-4.4km-on simulation, a reduced cloud base mass flux was used in the deep convection parameterization (Rackow et al., 2024). The global kilometer-scale atmosphere-only simulations with MPAS were made for the “DYnamics of the Atmospheric general circulation Modeled On Non-hydrostatic Domains” (DYAMOND) initiative (Judt & Rios-Berrios, 2021; Skamarock et al., 2012; Stevens et al., 2019). We analyze DYAMOND summer simulations (from August 1st to 8 September 2016) at 3.75 km and at 7.5 km resolution, run once with a scale-aware cumulus parameterization scheme and once with a fully active one. In the scale-aware simulations, most of the precipitation is resolved (Judt & Rios-Berrios, 2021). We also add the 3.75 km DYAMOND winter simulation (from January 20th to 1 March 2020) with scale-aware cumulus parameterization to our analysis. For simplicity, we will refer to the simulations with the scale-aware cumulus parameterization scheme as “deep convection parameterization off”. The simulations span different periods, but results are robust already for one season. In Table S1 in Supporting Information S1 we summarize key aspects of the kilometer-scale simulations we use.

Furthermore, we utilize a number of AMIP style simulations of the CMIP6 ensemble with a horizontal resolution higher or equal to $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ (Eyring et al., 2016) (for the period 1979–2014, see Text S1 in Supporting Information S1 for the list of models) as low resolution model reference.

As observation reference for daily rainfall accumulation we use three global gridded precipitation data sets that are satellite-based and gauge-corrected: IMERG version 07 final run (Huffman et al., 2023), MSWEP V2.2 (Beck

et al., 2019) and GPCP version 1.3 (Adler et al., 2017). For the analysis we select an overlapping period from 2001 to 2020. We refer to satellite-based data simply as observations. In addition, we also include gauge measurement series from 1994 to 1999 (NOAA National Centers of Environmental Information, 1999).

To ensure an accurate comparison, we conservatively interpolate all 2D fields to a common $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid, before performing further analysis. For ICON, fully conservative remapping from the Healpix output grid is not possible, so we use the Healpix resolution closest to $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ and nearest-neighbor interpolation. We choose this resolution to allow comparison with CMIP6 models. It should be noted that going to coarser resolutions will smooth out precipitation variability, and some of the signal will be lost.

2.2. Autocorrelation Diagnostic

We calculate the lag- τ autocorrelation r_s for the daily accumulated precipitation time series $X(t)$ for every grid cell. Although our results are robust to the choice of the correlation coefficient, we differ from Roehrig et al. (2013), in that we do not use the Pearson coefficient, but the Spearman coefficient. The latter measures how well a given relationship between two variables (in our case between a time series and a copy of that same time series shifted by lag = τ) can be described by a monotonic function, rather than a linear function. We believe that this approach is more suitable for daily precipitation. r_s is defined as follows:

$$r_s = \rho_{R(X), R(X)}(\tau) = \frac{\text{cov}(R(X_{t+\tau}), R(X_t))}{\text{var}(R(X), R(X))}. \quad (1)$$

Here $\text{cov}(R(X_{t+\tau}), R(X_t))$ is the autocovariance of the rank R of X , which is normalized by the variance $\text{var}(R(X), R(X))$, which means $r_s \in [-1, 1]$. Overbars denote time means. Like Roehrig et al. (2013), we use a lag of $\tau = 1$ because at this timescale the autocorrelation potentially captures the influence of large-scale processes such as CCEWs on precipitation, while our focus on daily accumulation implies that the persistence effect of processes such as afternoon rainfall initiation over soil moisture anomalies (Moon, Guillod, et al., 2019) are not considered. We investigate individual seasons, so the ranks R range from 1 to 92 for the JAS season, for example. From here on, we will refer to the lag-1 autocorrelation simply as autocorrelation.

2.3. Wave Filtering

We apply the wave filtering method developed by Wheeler and Kiladis (1999) to analyze five types of CCEWs, the MJO, and tropical depression (TD) type waves. Ordered from low frequency (LF) to high frequency (HF): MJO, equatorial Rossby (ER), mixed Rossby gravity (MRG), Kelvin, TD, eastward inertio-gravity (EIG, with $n = 0$) and westward inertio-gravity (WIG, with $n = 1$) waves. For simplicity, we will refer to all waves as CCEWs. For the filtering we use the full time-series, between 20°S and 20°N . We furthermore remove the first three harmonics of the seasonal cycle, detrend the signal and taper the ends to zero, as described by Wheeler and Kiladis (1999). To retain the full wave signal in regions where convection only occurs in one hemisphere, we do not apply a symmetric/antisymmetric decomposition (Kiladis et al., 2009). The filter parameters for the different wave types are the same as in Schlueter et al. (2019) for all waves except WIG waves, for which we choose the parameters in Wheeler and Kiladis (1999). We moreover distinguish between LF-Kelvin and HF-Kelvin waves, with a cutoff frequency of 0.2 day^{-1} . While the cutoff choice is somewhat arbitrary (given the smooth frequency spectrum of rainfall shown in Figure 3 and the broad-band nature of Kelvin waves variability), it has the advantage of making the lower frequency limit of the HF-Kelvin waves match the one of the TD and the EIG waves. LF-Kelvin and HF-Kelvin share the cutoff frequency, which results in a small overlap of the filters. The Kelvin wave splitting is still relevant, however, since the autocorrelation corresponds to the ratio of high frequency to low frequency variance on the order of a few days, and the Kelvin filter band ranges from 0.05 to 0.4 day^{-1} . We will refer to MJO, ER, MRG and LF-Kelvin as LF-CCEWs and to HF-Kelvin, TD, EIG and WIG as HF-CCEWs. The filtering is done using a Python script, which we partly based on Miyachi (2012) and Medeiros (2023). We validated the script by comparing our results for the IMERG data against the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission based results in Schlueter et al. (2019). We estimate the variance of precipitation explained by CCEWs by calculating the squared Pearson correlation coefficient between the precipitation anomalies (without the first three harmonics of the seasonal cycle, detrended and tapered) and the wave-filtered precipitation anomalies respectively (Schlueter et al., 2019).

Figure 1. Lag-1 autocorrelation of daily precipitation on a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid, datapoints with less than 1 mm/day mean precipitation are masked. First column for JAS, second column for DJF. Observation mean (IMERG, MSWEP and GPCP) in the first row, ICON-5km in the second row, IFS-4.4km-off in the third row, MPAS-3.75km-off in the fourth row and the CMIP6 model mean in the last row. MPAS-3.75km-off data does not cover the full JAS and DJF seasons. The circles in (a) and (b) indicate gauge station data. Stations with less than 1 mm/day mean precipitation are not shown. Dark gray dashed lines and the dark gray box in the last row indicate the domains for the further analysis: the Sahel domain (10°E – 30°W , 5°N – 15°N) the tropical domain (20°S – 20°N) and the CCEW domain (5°N – 15°N).

3. Results

3.1. Lag-1 Autocorrelation of Daily Precipitation in the Tropics

The autocorrelation pattern for daily precipitation in the tropics described by Roehrig et al. (2013) for GPCP is also apparent for IMERG and MSWEP, with minor differences in the absolute values (see Figure S1 in Supporting Information S1). The mean of the three gridded observations is depicted as a reference for the simulations in the first row of Figure 1, together with gauge station data (indicated by the circles). There are some outliers when comparing the gauge stations with the gridded observations, for example, in southern Mexico, where individual stations show very low autocorrelation values. We do not believe that the differences are due to the different periods covered by the satellite and ground-based observations, since there is very little interannual variability in the autocorrelation. Instead, we believe that the differences are due to the local perspective of the stations, while the satellite-based grid cells cover an area of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$.

Over the vast majority of the tropics, and especially over the ocean, the autocorrelation is positive, as highlighted by the averaged autocorrelation values depicted in Figure 2 for July–September (JAS). During JAS, there are two distinctive exceptional regions, the Sahel together with equatorial Africa and the northernmost part of South America at the border to Central America, with considerably lower (slightly negative) values of autocorrelation. During DJF, regions with similarly low autocorrelation are located in Africa south of the equator and in South America. To some extent, parts of the maritime continent also show considerably lower autocorrelation values than the surrounding ocean during DJF. These patterns cannot simply be described as a land-sea contrast, as clarified by the consistently high autocorrelation over the Asian monsoon and the Gulf of Mexico regions. From here on, we will focus on JAS, since the most pronounced low autocorrelation exists during this season over Africa, where we will more specifically focus on the Sahel domain.

Figure 2. Mean lag-1 autocorrelation of daily precipitation calculated for July-September (JAS) for different domains. First row: the Sahel domain (10°E–35°W, 5°N–15°N). Second row: tropical land. Third row: tropical ocean (20°S–20°N). Depicted in the first column from the left are the values for the observations, in the second column the values for simulations without deep convection parameterization and in the third column the values for simulations with active deep convection parameterization. Uncertainty bars indicate interannual variability, calculated as the standard deviation. For the CMIP6 bars, the larger gray colorbar shows the intermodel variability, calculated as the standard deviation. Gridpoints with less than 1 mm/day mean precipitation are not included.

The multi-model mean autocorrelation of a broad selection of CMIP6 simulations (see last row of Figure 1) captures the observed pattern in broad strokes (spatial correlation with observations is 0.7 for JAS and 0.85 for DJF). However, the persistence of precipitation is overestimated everywhere and especially over the Sahel. This is summarized by the averaged autocorrelation values in Figure 2. The drastic overestimation of the autocorrelation in the Sahel domain is similar to the findings of Roehrig et al. (2013) for CMIP5 models. The CMIP6 models also overestimate the autocorrelation over tropical land and ocean, although the difference with observations is smaller over the ocean. These low resolution GCM models all use deep convection parameterization schemes; we next contrast their behavior with kilometer-scale models without convective parameterizations.

The maps in the second row of Figure 1 depict the autocorrelation maps for ICON-5km. The model captures key features of the observations, especially the presence of regions with low autocorrelation, with the African region during JAS being the most pronounced. Mean autocorrelation values are within or very close to the observation range for the entire tropical region (see Figure 2).

The autocorrelation maps for IFS-4.4km-off are displayed in the third row of Figure 1. Again, the pattern matches the observations, but is a little noisier than the observation mean and ICON-5km since only 1 year is available for this model setup. Nevertheless, this shows that a single season is already enough for the autocorrelation pattern to appear. The mean autocorrelation values for IFS-4.4km-off in Figure 2 are slightly above the observation range across the tropics.

Figure 3. Relative power spectra calculated from daily precipitation for July–September (JAS), smoothed with a 3-day running window. First row: the Sahel domain (10°E–35°W, 5°N–15°N). Second row: tropical land. Third row: tropical ocean (20°S–20°N). Depicted in the first column from the left are the values for the observations, in the second column the values for the simulations without deep convection parameterization and in the third column the values for the simulations with active deep convection parameterization. Gray shaded areas indicate the observation range and turquoise shading the CMIP6 intermodel spread calculated as the standard deviation. Gridpoints with less than 1 mm/day mean precipitation are not included.

A number of additional simulations with the IFS model, produced within the nextGEMS project are available. IFS-4.4km-on, was run with the deep convection scheme turned on, but a reduced vertical mass flux. Additionally, there are the 9 km simulations IFS-9km-off and IFS-9km-on. These simulations allow us to explore the influence of the deep convection parameterization scheme on the autocorrelation in the IFS model. Autocorrelation increases over the Sahel, tropical land and tropical ocean in IFS simulations with active deep convection parameterization for both the 4.4 and the 9 km resolutions (see Figure 2). The fact that the increase is seen across the tropics, including oceans, suggests that land surface-atmosphere interactions are not driving factors for changes in the autocorrelation when the deep convection parameterization is turned on.

The 39-day MPAS-3.75km-off simulation generally also captures the autocorrelation pattern, as shown in the fourth row of Figure 1. However, the model produces autocorrelation values below the observation range, as can be seen from Figure 2. This bias is smaller for MPAS-7.5km-off.

The mean autocorrelation values for the four MPAS simulations in Figure 2 are consistent with the influence of the deep convection parameterization on the autocorrelation in IFS. As for IFS, the autocorrelation increases when the deep convection parameterization is turned on. The increase is stronger over the Sahel than over the rest of the tropics in MPAS.

The increase in autocorrelation when the deep convection parameterization is turned on is caused by a decrease in high frequency variance (meaning on the time-scale of a few days) relative to low frequency variance in IFS and MPAS. This is demonstrated in Figure 3, which depicts the mean relative power spectra of daily precipitation for the same regions as in Figure 2 for the observations (individual data set in the left column, observation range repeated throughout for ease of comparison), the models with explicit convection (middle column), and the models with parameterized convection (right column).

When IFS is run with deep convection parameterization, the power spectra are closer to the CMIP6 range, whereas when it is run with deep convection treated explicitly, the power spectra agree much better with the observation range and ICON-5km. MPAS tends to overestimate the high frequency variance, when the deep convection parameterization is turned off, corresponding to the low autocorrelation values.

3.2. CCEW Contribution to Precipitation Variance

A considerable fraction of the precipitation variance underlying the power spectra presented in Figure 3 is related to CCEWs (e.g., Schlueter et al. (2019)). To investigate the influence of CCEWs on the autocorrelation, we therefore compute the precipitation variance fraction for the different wave types in the CCEW domain (5°N–15°N), which largely coincides with the seasonal position of the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) and includes the Sahel domain (see Figure 1). Apart from the Sahel domain, the CCEW domain does not contain much land, so we only distinguish between ocean and Sahel in the CCEW analysis. Following Schlueter et al. (2019), we calculate the precipitation variance fraction as the squared Pearson correlation coefficients between latitudinal mean precipitation anomalies and latitudinal mean wave-filtered precipitation anomalies. We subsequently take the respective longitudinal mean to generate the mean values presented in Figure 4. Since this correlation method does not take into account interactions between waves, the sum of the precipitation variance fractions attributed to CCEWs can be interpreted as the maximum variance fraction explainable by CCEWs (Schlueter et al., 2019). It should be noted that only a small part of the WIG frequency spectrum can be filtered from daily data, which is why these waves only contribute little.

The observation variance fractions in Figure 4 show a large contribution of HF-CCEWs, especially TD waves, to the total variance over the Sahel, whereas over the ocean LF-CCEWs dominate. HF-CCEWs affect the power spectrum by adding power to the high frequency end, corresponding to low autocorrelation values; LF-CCEWs have the opposite effect. This and the additional results presented in Text S2 for IMERG demonstrate the importance of CCEWs in the origin of the observed autocorrelation pattern.

The models with parameterized deep convection have one thing in common: they overestimate the contribution of LF-CCEWs relative to HF-CCEWs, which is consistent with the overestimation of the low frequency end of the power spectrum and the overestimation of the autocorrelation. This bias is lowest for IFS-4.4km-on, which agrees well with the comparatively low bias of this model in the power spectra.

The ICON-5km simulation produces CCEW variance fractions close the observation range, although it overestimates the TD wave fraction over the Sahel.

In both IFS simulations with explicit deep convection, the LF-CCEW fraction decreases compared to the simulations with parameterized deep convection, while the HF-CCEW fraction is lower than in the observations, resulting in underestimated total CCEW fractions. However, the ratio of HF-CCEW fraction to LF-CCEW fraction is higher with explicit deep convection, which is related to the lower autocorrelation.

In the MPAS simulations with deep convection treated explicitly, the LF-CCEW fraction also decreases compared to the simulations with parameterized deep convection, but at the same time the HF-CCEW fraction increases. As a result, the simulations overestimate the total wave fraction over the Sahel. This corresponds nicely to the overestimation of the high frequency end of the power spectra and the low autocorrelation in these simulations.

Summarizing the influence of CCEWs on the autocorrelation pattern in the models, we find a relationship between the relative importance of HF-CCEWs and LF-CCEWs, power spectra and autocorrelation. However, an unbiased representation of CCEW variances is not required or implied for correct autocorrelation and vice versa.

Figure 4. Precipitation variance fractions attributed to convectively coupled equatorial waves (CCEWs) calculated as the squared Pearson correlation between precipitation anomalies and wave-filtered precipitation anomalies for July–September (JAS). In the first row calculated for the Sahel domain (10°E–35°W, 5°N–15°N) and in the second row for tropical ocean in the CCEW domain (5°N–15°N). The left column shows the observations, the middle column the simulations without deep convection parameterization, and the right the simulations with active deep convection parameterization. The numbers give the ratio of the summed variance fractions of the high frequency CCEWs to the summed variance fractions of the low frequency CCEWs. Black uncertainty bars indicate the interannual variability of the summed variance fractions, calculated as the standard deviation over the years. The gray uncertainty bar indicates the intermodel variability of the summed variance fractions of the CMIP6 models, calculated as the standard deviation. Gridpoints with less than 1 mm/day mean precipitation are not included.

4. Conclusions

We study the lag-1 autocorrelation of daily precipitation as an easy-to-compute diagnostic of tropical precipitation variability in kilometer-scale climate models. The diagnostic is useful for investigating the persistence of precipitation across the tropics and also provides information on precipitation power spectra and the relative importance of high frequency and low frequency convectively coupled equatorial waves in modulating rainfall variability.

Our results show that the autocorrelation pattern first presented by Roehrig et al. (2013) is robust across satellite-based observations and gauge stations. The pattern can be summarized as one of largest autocorrelation over ocean; smaller, but still positive autocorrelation over tropical land; and much smaller or even negative autocorrelation in the core of the rainy regions of Africa and South America. The kilometer-scale simulations of ICON and IFS from the nextGEMS project and to some extent also the MPAS DYAMOND simulations capture the observed autocorrelation values, in contrast to a wide range of CMIP6 models. In the IFS model the

autocorrelation is comparable to observations when the deep convection is simulated explicitly, but overestimated across land and ocean when the deep convection parameterization is turned on. This effect occurs for two horizontal resolutions and even if the parameterized vertical mass flux is strongly reduced. Hence, we find that precipitation persistence has a distinct dependence on the representation of deep convection, rather than simply on horizontal resolution. This dependence is confirmed by our analysis of global kilometer-scale MPAS simulations, which also show lower autocorrelation values with explicitly simulated deep convection than with parameterized deep convection. The same effect occurs over land and ocean, indicating that soil-moisture feedbacks at the surface are not involved in the improvement of rainfall persistence.

We show that the autocorrelation is a good indicator of the underlying precipitation power spectra. The nextGEMS models that explicitly treat deep convection perform particularly well compared to the observation power spectra. The MPAS simulations with explicitly simulated deep convection overestimate power in the high frequencies of the spectrum. Simulations with deep convection parameterization, in contrast, underestimate the power in the high frequencies. How exactly parameterized convection reddens variability is not yet clear.

We attribute precipitation variance to different types of CCEWs. Our observation analysis demonstrates the importance of the relation between HF-CCEWs and LF-CCEWs for the origin of the autocorrelation pattern, in addition to other possible mechanisms such as land-atmosphere interactions for the Sahel (e.g., Taylor et al. (2013)). ICON-5km, which produces autocorrelation values within or close to the observation range, also produces CCEW fractions close to the observations. When deep convection is parameterized, the variance fraction of LF-CCEWs becomes too strong, which corresponds to the underestimation of power in the high frequencies of the spectrum and the overestimation of autocorrelation. The autocorrelation thus contains information about the relative importance of HF-CCEWs and LF-CCEWs, although it is not a sufficient indicator for the overall correct representation of CCEWs in a model.

Autocorrelation is an easily computed metric that encapsulates many underlying atmospheric processes and provides a simple diagnostic for tropical precipitation variability in GCMs. Our finding that kilometer-scale models are able to reproduce the observed autocorrelation pattern and mean magnitude furthermore demonstrates that these models offer a unique possibility to study tropical precipitation and its relation to atmospheric dynamics.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest relevant to this study.

Data Availability Statement

The NextGEMS data is archived by the Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ) and can be accessed via DKRZ's supercomputer Levante after registration <https://luv.dkrz.de/register/>. DYAMOND MPAS data was retrieved from the DKRZ archive <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/index.html>. The CMIP6 model data can be obtained from the Earth System Grid Foundation. IMERG data were accessed via NASA's Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center (https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/datasets/GPM_3IMERGDF_07/summary?keywords=%22IMERG%20final%22). MSWEP data were accessed via <https://www.gloh2o.org/mswep/>. GPCP data can be obtained from <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/metadata/landing-page/bin/iso?id=gov.noaa.ncdc:C00999>. The gauge data were accessed via <http://iridl.ldeo.columbia.edu/SOURCES/NOAA/NCDC/DAI-LY/GLOBALSOD/?sem=iridl%3ADCAtmosphere>. The post-processed data and the analysis scripts are available under <https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/detail/o:2086159> (Spät, 2024).

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